

From Monitoring to Geo-mechanical Digital Twin: A First Step in the Reliable Prediction of Landslide Processes

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Abstract

Landslides are highly destructive events which pose significant risks to human lives, infrastructure and environment. Accurately predicting landslide processes is crucial for effective hydrogeological risk mitigation and disaster management. Traditional monitoring techniques have provided valuable data on slope behavior, but their limitations in real-time analysis have hindered accurate predictions. To overcome these constraints, an innovative method is proposed, integrating a Geo-mechanical Digital Twin based on advanced geotechnical models, real-time back analysis and deep-learning techniques. The automatic update of the Finite element (FE) model of the slope in the Salorno area (BZ) was developed in the framework of the innovative WeStatiX SHM [1] platform. This model has facilitated the creation of numerical simulations of the site at-risk, leading to a deeper understanding of the future events. Through the integration of sensor data in real time, this approach enhances ongoing analysis and anticipation of possible failure mechanisms. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and real-time data provides early warning signals. The advancement presented here has the potential to minimize the impact on communities and critical assets, ultimately improving disaster management practices through interdisciplinary collaborations and standardized protocols.

Keywords: Geo-mechanical Digital Twin, Artificial Intelligence, Real-time back analysis, Finite Element Modelling, Landslides prediction, Real-time monitoring, Crack propagation

1 Introduction

A landslide can be defined as the swift movement of the mass of a rock, residual soil, or sediments adjacent to a slope, characterized by the downward and outward displacement of the mass's center of gravity. As devastating natural disasters, they have the potential to result in human fatalities, severe economic repercussions and the destruction of the vital infrastructure, as well as cultural and natural heritage. Additionally, the climate changes have a significant impact on the stability of both natural and engineered slopes, leading to consequential effects on landslide occurrences.

Traditional monitoring techniques have yielded valuable information about the behavior of slopes; however, their ability to provide real-time analysis and precise predictions has been constrained by certain limitations. Conventionally, simulations have been used for years to define thresholds for monitoring geotechnical conditions. These thresholds, typically based on displacement values, help determine whether a slope is in danger or not. Yet, the challenge lies in the fact that the system evolves over time and requires periodic recalculations and simulations to accurately assess and adjust these thresholds and predict future scenarios. It is, of course, impractical to manually repeat these time consuming recalculations.

We propose a novel approach based on the integration of a Geo-mechanical Digital Twin, AI and real-time back analysis to continuously evaluate the stability of geological formations. Unlike traditional methods, our technique leverages the power of AI to enable continuous, real-time slope stability assessment and forecasting. Instead of relying on a limited number of simulations to define static thresholds, the digital twin gets continuously adjusted to minimize the discrepancy with measurements, leading to dynamically evolving thresholds and highly reliable simulations. By employing advanced nonlinear constitutive models, a unique methodology was introduced, which has surpassed previous attempts at accurately capturing the complex behavior of this type of material. It provides more accurate and up-to-date assessments of the ground behavior. Through the automatic identification of parameters based on data input, the system adapts to geological formation changes over time.

Key publications in the field have emphasized the need for improved predictive capabilities in landslide research [2, 3]. Controversial and diverging hypotheses have emerged regarding the influence of various geological and environmental factors on landslide initiation and propagation.

This underscores the importance of developments in the field by incorporating advanced geotechnical models and real-time monitoring data to improve the prediction accuracy. By assimilating real-time sensor data into the computational model, continuous analysis and prediction of potential failure mechanisms is enabled.

While the proposed technique can be applied to various scenarios, such as the assessment of bridge reliability and lifespan or validation of building construction, its application in the context of slope stability evaluation is specifically highlighted as an exemplary case study. It is focused on an area situated on the left side of the Adige Valley within the municipality of

Figure 1: Visual representation of the digital twin operation.

Salorno (Bolzano, Italy). The slope under investigation overlooks a cultivated quarry area, a drainage known as Fossa di Salorno, as well as the Abetone and Brenner State Road (S.S. 12). Over the recent years, the slope has experienced multiple instances of collapses of different magnitudes, resulting in the closure of the roads essential for daily traffic. A peculiar analysis of the rock mass revealed that the existing fragile structures and discontinuities represented the main predisposing factors for the rock fall, which underscored the critical significance of monitoring for this site.

Figure 2: (a) Geological map and (b) orthophotos.

2 Geological outlines and history of the site

The historical events surrounding the slope in Salorno (BZ) have played a significant role in shaping the understanding and management of the area. These events have not only stressed the geological challenges faced, but have also prompted crucial interventions and measures to ensure the safety of the region and its inhabitants.

Figure 3: The fracture in Salorno area (around 60m long).[10]

The following chronological list provides an overview of the noteworthy occurrences that have taken place, highlighting the critical milestones and their impact.

- 15 December 2011 - evacuation and clearing the land parcels located at the foot of the slope; closure to traffic of the S.S.12 by the Roads Office of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano;
- 19 December 2011 - the Geology and Materials Testing Office authorized the construction of an additional protective wall, supplementing to the existing ones, with indicative dimensions of 120 m length and 4 m height;
- 10 November 2012 - a continuous descent of medium-small rock from the already affected wall, which prompted the intervention of the Geology and Material Testing Office followed by evaluation from the Roads Office of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano;
- 19 January 2013 - in just a few hours, the main crack had manifested noticeable movements, surpassing the recorded activity of the previous two months, which led to the closure of the traffic in the area;
- 21 January 2013 – extension of the protective wall to length of 150 m;
- 1 March 2013 - a discharge of material quantified in a few thousand cubic meters was recorded, which breached the protective wall and impacted the S.S.12;

- 10 June 2013 - several rocks detached from the southern rock face of Salorno at km 402+800 of the S.S.12; the material, consisting of highly fractured limestone of the Contrin formation came loose from the same area of the rockfall of 1 March 2013;
- 25 June - 5 July 2013 - raising the existing wall to 6 m height;
- The night of 25-26 May 2014 - another collapse (an approx. 1000 m³ large rock), which fortunately came to a halt within the protective wall, but led to a new precautionary closure of the S.S. 12, triggered a dust cloud and carried the trees located at the base of the wall.

To minimize the closures stated earlier, five potentiometric displacement transducers and a resistance thermometer were installed in October 2012 (Figure 4), in order to monitor the crack evolution, which is primarily attributed to tension effects associated with freeze-thaw cycles. Nevertheless, the contribution of shear forces is also considered in the simulation. For gathering the data on the slope's behavior, a receiver powered by a photovoltaic panel was utilized. This receiver collects sensor data every 12 hours and transfers it directly to the Waterstones S.rl.[18] server through a GPRS modem. The collected data includes the cumulative monthly displacement measured by each transducer, which can be correlated with the average temperature and rainfall recorded at the meteorological station of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano during the same period.

Figure 4: Potentiometric displacement transducers and a resistance thermometer installed in Salorno.[12]

After six years of continuous monitoring from 2012 to 2019, the results consistently indicated a general trend of widening across all sections of the fracture. The relative speed of this widening trend ranged between 3-6 mm/year during the period from 2016 to 2019.

On the 21st September 2021, the east portion records a total opening of around 20 mm for the Fe1 and approximately 25 mm for the Fe2. The west portion records a total opening

with double/triple the magnitude: Fe3 with opening of about 63 mm, Fe4 with an opening of approximately 51 mm and Fe5 with an opening of roughly 60 mm. In Figure 5, three distinct zones are visible. In light blue is marked the detached portion in 2017, while in yellow and green two additional zones separated by a discontinuity are shown. One specific fracture was noticed, which is positioned a few meters above of the rockfall edge and spans approximately 60 meters in length (Figure 3).

Figure 5: Representation of the crack opening in 2021.[11]

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Simulation methodology

The nonlinear simulation begins starting from in-situ stress state due to the rock weight and evolves further from the first day of monitoring, depending on time and temperature.

As also underlined in section 3.3, the main mechanism governing the progressive crack opening is assumed to be related by the cycles of freezing and thawing, and the pressure generated by ice formation within the crack, that exerts on its walls due to volumetric increase. This interpretation is motivated by the observation that indicates a correlation between crack behavior and temperature fluctuations shown in Figure 7. The water infiltration has the additional effect of reducing the friction between the crack walls, contributing to crack propagation.

The finite element mesh is created with several discontinuities better described later in Table 5, employing advanced cohesive elements. This type of elements have been selected as they incorporate the concept of damage, which represents the deterioration or loss of structural integrity along the interface or crack. As the cohesive element experiences loading, it undergoes progressive damage, resulting in a reduction in stiffness and strength. Furthermore, cohesive elements capture the softening behavior of the material, where the resistance to separation diminishes as the crack propagates. As the slope geometry and crack location are known precisely, this approach was deemed to be more suitable compared to the Extended Finite Element

Method (XFEM).

A specific pressure on both sides of the monitored crack's bottom is applied and the discontinuity is evaluated considering seven different cross-sections, taking into account the different sensor measurements. As new measurement data is gathered, the force required to generate the observed opening in the upper part of the crack is iteratively calculated, taking into account the damage and plastic strain accumulated from the start of the monitoring until the day corresponding to the current simulation.

Throughout the process, the utilization factor is continuously assessed using the shear strength reduction (SSR) method. This involves adjusting the equivalent cohesion and friction angle of the rock to determine the current level of safety. These constitutive parameters are incrementally decreased until failure occurs, or increased until a safe condition is achieved. The breaking condition is represented by the non-convergence of the numerical solution, that is, the moment when the algorithm is no longer able to converge and equilibrium is violated. The multiplier of the constitutive parameters at failure represents the factor of safety.

The analysis provides information on the stress and deformation state of the rock at each point. Corresponding to each measurement, the model is updated and the results are immediately made available via browser to the cloud platform users.

Additionally, the macroscopic properties of the ground are evaluated and continually recalculated to track changes over time. By combining the collected data with simulations, reliable predictions can be made and the trend of displacements and safety factors for the next year analyzed. Factors such as the current opening velocity and the ground's elastic spring-back are carefully considered in the final stage of analysis.

3.2 Material properties

The base material properties used for simulation were identified in [4] through experimental testing and employing the RSDData [13] software. Tests were performed to determine the mechanical properties and strength parameters of the different rock materials composing the geological formation.

Commonly used parameters in rock mechanics are defined in the scope of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion and the Hoek-Brown criterion.

The Mohr-Coulomb [14] criterion is a mathematical expression that relates the shear stress and normal stress acting on a plane within a material. The criterion is based on the concept of an idealized failure envelope in the principal stress space, represented by a straight line with a slope equal to the internal friction angle (ϕ) of the material. The equation for the Mohr-Coulomb criterion is:

$$\tau = c + \sigma \cdot \tan(\phi) \quad (1)$$

where:

- τ - the shear stress;

- c - the cohesion (intercept of the failure envelope);
- σ - the normal stress acting on the plane;
- ϕ - the friction angle.

According to the Mohr-Coulomb criterion, failure occurs when the shear stress on a plane reaches the maximum shear strength of the material. This criterion is commonly used in geotechnical engineering [15] for stability analysis of slopes, retaining walls, dams [16] and foundations, as well as in rock mechanics for the assessment of rock mass stability.

On the other hand, the Hoek-Brown criterion[5] is a more advanced criterion that takes into account the rock's intact strength, the effects of deformation and damage, and the influence of the rock mass properties. The Hoek-Brown criterion introduces additional parameters such as the Geological Strength Index (GSI) and the rock mass quality index. The Generalised Hoek-Brown failure criterion [7] for jointed rock masses is expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_3 + \sigma_{ci} \left(m_b \frac{\sigma_3}{\sigma_{ci}} + s \right)^a, \quad (2)$$

where:

- σ_1 and σ_3 - the maximum and the minimum effective principal stress at failure;
- m_b - the value of the Hoek-Brown constant for the rock mass;
- σ_{ci} - the uniaxial compressive strength of the intact rock pieces;
- s and a - constants that depend on the rock mass properties.

The slope under examination has revealed two main rock formations, namely Giovo and Contrin, which contain the majority of the dangerous discontinuities [4]. Given the considerable structural variability observed across different sections in the formation Contrin, it becomes necessary to divide it into three distinct zones. These zones are characterized by varying values of the geological strength index (GSI) of the rock. This stratification takes into account the different geological properties and strengths exhibited within each zone.

GSI values typically range from 0 to 100, with higher values indicating better rock mass quality and lower values indicating poor rock mass conditions [9].

The Hoek-Brown model has been widely validated and applied in various engineering projects, including underground excavations, tunneling, slope stability analysis, and rock slope engineering [6].

The identified constitutive parameters can be used to perform macroscopic simulations of rock behavior and stability. By fitting the Mohr-Coulomb criterion or the Hoek-Brown criterion to the test results, it is possible to obtain reliable strength parameters for the rock material, among which global strength is essentially important for the macroscopic simulation. This

enables accurate predictions of rock behavior under different loading and environmental conditions.

In the following subsections, the material characteristics of the slope formations utilized in the calculations are provided. These properties, among the rest, encompass cohesion, friction angle, uniaxial compressive strength and the elastic modulus.

3.2.1 Formation Giovo

Hoek-Brown Classification	
UCS of intact rock [MPa]	185
GSI	60
mi	8
Disturbance factor D	0
Intact modulus [MPa]	166500
Hoek-Brown Criterion	
mb	1.917
s	0.0117
a	0.503
Rock Mass Parameters	
Tensile strength [MPa]	1.133
UCS [MPa]	19.797
Global strength [MPa]	36.683
Elastic modulus [MPa]	86580
Mohr-Columb Fit	
Friction angle [°]	49.25
Cohesion [MPa]	3.515

Table 1: Rock material properties for the formation Giovo[13].

3.2.2 Formation Contrin

The following figures clearly illustrate the three zones within the Contrin formation and provide a visual representation of their respective characteristics.

Figure 6

Zone 1

Hoek-Brown Classification	
UCS of intact rock [MPa]	185
GSI	60
mi	9
Disturbance factor D	0
Intact modulus [MPa]	78625
Hoek-Brown Criterion	
mb	2.157
s	0.0117
a	0.503
Rock Mass Parameters	
Tensile strength [MPa]	1.007
UCS [MPa]	19.797
Global strength [MPa]	36.683
Elastic modulus [MPa]	40885
Mohr-Columb Fit	
Friction angle [°]	50.34
Cohesion [MPa]	3.460

Table 2: Rock material properties for the formation Contrin in the first zone[13].

Zone 2

Hoek-Brown Classification	
UCS of intact rock [MPa]	185
GSI	45
mi	9
Disturbance factor D	0
Intact modulus [MPa]	78625
Hoek-Brown Criterion	
mb	1.262
s	0.0022
a	0.508
Rock Mass Parameters	
Tensile strength [MPa]	0.325
UCS [MPa]	8.293
Global strength [MPa]	27.458
Elastic modulus [MPa]	17584.48
Mohr-Columb Fit	
Friction angle [°]	47.03
Cohesion [MPa]	2.021

Table 3: Rock material properties for the formation Contrin in the second zone[13].

Zone 3

Hoek-Brown Classification	
UCS of intact rock [MPa]	185
GSI	70
mi	9
Disturbance factor D	0
Intact modulus [MPa]	78625
Hoek-Brown Criterion	
mb	3.083
s	0.0357
a	0.501
Rock Mass Parameters	
Tensile strength [MPa]	2.141
UCS [MPa]	34.785
Global strength [MPa]	48.988
Elastic modulus [MPa]	57617.51
Mohr-Columb Fit	
Friction angle [°]	51.64
Cohesion [MPa]	3.083

Table 4: Rock material properties for the formation Contrin in the third zone.[13]

3.3 Data analysis

In the current geological monitoring practices, the focus is primarily on measuring the opening of discontinuities or displacements of geological formations and providing this information to the authorities responsible for their management. However, the interpretation of the data can be highly challenging. Commonly, calculations are periodically performed by experts, to determine the significance of the measurements. Unfortunately, this process can be cumbersome and time-consuming, making it practically impossible for real-time stability assessment. Moreover, this process makes interpretation intrinsically subjective and dependent on the evaluator.

To address these limitations, the new strategy goes beyond mere measurement and provides continuous, objective and reliable analysis. By combining data acquired on site through detailed geological surveys, measurements at specific points, and advanced technologies such as real-time inverse analysis, geomechanical simulation and artificial intelligence, it is possible to improve the interpretation of monitoring data through a digital twin. Rather than relying on scattered calculations, a continuous evaluation of the data is enabled, eliminating the need for repetitive manual analyses. This makes it possible for the decision makers to have access to more reliable and up-to-date information about the stability of geological structures.

After observing the presence of the cracks in the slope, the data collected indicated the varying degrees of the crack opening, depending on temperature and rainfall. As shown in Figure 7, during the winter the crack has a tendency to propagate, which is assumed to be due to the freezing and thawing cycles and expansion of ice at crack's bottom. However, in the summer the crack tends to close, although the degree of closure became progressively lower over the years. This phenomenon suggests that the crack might be undergoing damage, resulting in reduced ability to close during the summer months.

In terms of predictions, the incorporated deep-learning model utilizes both temperature and rainfall data to enhance accuracy. Nevertheless, it should be noted that in only a few cases, rainfall has a significant influence on the crack behavior, as can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 7

Figure 8

3.4 Digital twin setup

By analysing the survey conducted by the company Cartorender[17], precise information regarding the slope's geometry, including the crack itself and its approximate depth, was obtained. A new laser scanner survey was performed on a larger area and led to an accurate and geo-referenced point cloud. The plane strain finite element model corresponding to the single rock wall cross-sections was developed based on the analysis of seven cross sections along the length of the analysed slope. The survey, together with the provided information about discontinuities in 5, allowed to estimate the depth and the direction of the cracks. Due to the high danger of rockfall, it was unfortunately not possible to perform a geomechanical survey and

scanline in situ, directly on the rock face. Instead, the survey has been performed by flyover. In addition, a geomechanical characterization using the areal method was carried out by Luchetta in [4] at the base of the slope, analysing about a hundred discontinuity planes for each lithology.

Figure 9: The horizontal displacements [m] of the whole rock wall model visualized in WeStatiX SHM[1].

As discussed in the previous sections, specific constitutive models tailored for rocks mechanics were employed in the simulation, taking into account in-situ stresses, time-dependent behavior, and temperature effects.

The 3D digital twin interface enables the user to inspect the model, evaluate up-to-date simulation results, to locate each sensor and interactively visualize the corresponding cross-section. The GUI further allows to visualize the deformed shape of the rock wall and to estimate the current depth of the monitored crack in each cross-section.

It is worth mentioning that the described methodology is fully compatible with Building Information Modeling (BIM), allowing smooth integration with other engineering processes, which enables a comprehensive understanding of the entire project's requirements and complexities.

Figure 10: The part of the mesh of the slope in WeStatiX SHM[1] with highlighted displacements. The red spherical icons represent the five potentiometric displacement transducers. The GUI allows interactive investigation of the cross section corresponding to the different devices by right-clicking on the corresponding icon.

By employing FE, the tensional and deformational state of the soil can be determined at each point. When constructing the geometric model, all identified families of discontinuities from the two rock formations were incorporated. These families were chosen based on observed spacing values at the global scale given in table 5, bearing in mind that the influence of spacing at the local scale is already considered in the geotechnical parameterization through the assignment of different GSI values to different zones.

Family of discontinuities	Formation Contrin		Formation Giovo	
	Inclination	Spacing [m]	Inclination	Spacing [m]
S	236/09	30	215/01	5
K1	355/78	60	195/84	5
K2	322/86	60	327/79	5
K3	268/88	30	104/88	5
K4	057/79	50	221/82	5

Table 5: Summary table of spacing values for each discontinuity family used in modeling[4].

Figure 11

Figure 12

When the values of utilization factor exceed the critical threshold, a pronounced concentration of shear stresses becomes apparent at the base of the slope (see Figure 13). Specifically, the deformation tends to propagate towards the primary fracture, which is assumed to exist within the slope. This observation aligns with the findings from ground surveys, where distinctive structures were observed at the bottom of the wall, potentially indicating damage phenomena at the foot of the slope.

The diagonal shear stress lines observed in the results (see Figure 13) highlight the areas where significant shear displacement occurs, posing a potential risk of rock damage, among which the shear displacement at the bottom section is of particular importance, as it indicates a potential failure mechanism. The uniform inclination across all modeled sections is a vital factor affecting the overall stability analysis, serving as a verification of the simulation's accuracy in capturing stress concentration. It is crucial to acknowledge and address these findings

to ensure the safety and integrity of the ground and surrounding structures.

Figure 13: Results for the cross sections Fe1, Fe2, Fe3, Fe4, Fe5, showing the shear stress indicating potential damage and the predicted crack openings [1].

4 Results of monitoring and predictive analytics

Figure 14

Data analysis and visualisation is enabled within a dedicated WeStatiX cloud interface[1], allowing for efficient and streamlined data processing. AI algorithms are leveraged to perform predictive analysis, enhancing the forecast of the future behavior of the slope, particularly in terms of crack propagation, temperature and stability. What sets this methodology apart is the automatic self-validation and self-improvement of the AI models over time, ensuring their accuracy and reliability. A hybrid approach is adopted, reinforcing and validating the AI models through numerical simulation results.

The analysis and 3D visualization of data is provided in a web dashboard for efficient data interpretation. The stability of the system is continuously evaluated by automatically executing FE analyses, allowing for real-time monitoring and assessment. To ensure accurate results, continuous model calibration is performed through inverse analysis techniques, enabling the refinement of the model parameters based on observed behavior. The system generates automatically user-downloadable monitoring reports, providing detailed measurement and simulation results for comprehensive analysis.

In Figure 15, several significant charts displayed on the monitoring platform are presented. These charts provide valuable indicators regarding the crack opening measured by each sensor, including the current measurements and the historical data from the previous year. Additionally, the reversibility of the crack opening, which indicates how much the crack closes during the summer period, as well as the velocity of the crack opening and the utilization factor, are also depicted.

Figure 15: The obtained charts in the Digital Twin monitoring platform.[1]

Upon closer examination, it is evident that sensors Fe1 and Fe2 exhibit noticeably lower crack openings compared to the other three sensors. This observation aligns with the results obtained from the numerical simulation regarding the displacement in the x-direction represented in Figure 10. The consistency between the numerical simulation and the monitoring data strengthens the confidence in the accuracy and reliability of the obtained results.

Figure 16: Representation of strain distribution on the Digital Twin, showing the Finite Element model mesh.[1]

An additional noteworthy observation pertains to the behavior of the crack in sensor Fe5. Analysis of the monitoring data reveals that, over the previous year, the crack has shown no significant increase in size, based on the measurements from this particular sensor. Moreover, the reversibility of the crack opening in Fe5 is observed to be remarkably low. These findings raise concerns among experts, as they indicate a potential failure scenario, which is also confirmed by a utilization factor of 98%. The limited reversibility suggests loss of elasticity in the

rock, due to progressive damage. The combination of these factors highlights the importance of closely monitoring and evaluating the behavior of the crack in sensor Fe5 to accurately assess the risk of potential failure.

Raw data is collected from the sensors and processed using a specialized algorithm integrated into the monitoring platform. This algorithm plays a crucial role in smoothing the data and removing any irregularities. The ability to smooth the data and remove outliers is particularly significant because it helps to mitigate the impact of sudden jumps that may occur in the sensor readings. Beside the redefinition of the instrument scale, there can be several reasons for these jumps in the sensor data, including:

- Environmental factors - sudden changes in environmental conditions, such as temperature, humidity, or external vibrations;
- Sensor malfunction - occasionally, sensors may experience technical issues or malfunctions, leading to inconsistent readings (these malfunctions could be caused by factors such as faulty calibration, electrical interference, or physical damage);
- Human interference - in some cases, manual adjustments or interventions made by individuals during the monitoring process can mistakenly introduce abrupt changes in the sensor data;
- Natural events - certain natural events or phenomena, such as seismic activity or ground movement, can generate rapid variations in the sensor readings.

Figure 17: Raw data for the crack opening coming from the sensors[1].

Figure 18: The product of data smoothing in the monitoring platform[1].

In the graphs obtained for the sensors Fe1 (Figure 19) and sensor Fe3 (Figure 20), the relationship between the crack opening and the temperature can be observed. In light blue the predictive displacement for the next year is marked, while in the dark blue the historical data gathered from the sensors is denoted. Comparing these graphs with the charts presented in Figure 15, a correlation can be made. Specifically, for sensor Fe1, a relatively high reversibility factor of 72.7% is observed, indicating that the crack is still closing to some extent during the summer period. However, for sensor Fe3, the reversibility factor is only 2.4%, indicating minimal crack closure during the summer. This contributes to the flattening of the displacement curve, implying a significant loss of ground elasticity.

Figure 19: The forecast displacement charts obtained in WeStatiX SHM [1] for sensor Fe1.

Figure 20: The forecast displacement charts obtained in WeStatiX SHM [1] for sensor Fe3.

Gathering additional data leads to improved predictions. Error assessment was carried out using specific forecast accuracy metrics. The predictive capabilities are enhanced by the application of deep learning models in the WeStatiX SHM [1] platform. The model demonstrates low discrepancy and remains accurate for temperature and displacement forecast for a one-year period. As time progresses, the model tends to improve and become more accurate.

Figure 21: Predictions of the displacement in each sensor and the temperature based on previous data.

Metric Sensor	Area Between Curves	End Point Error	MASE	SMAPE
Fe1	0.030142	0.059975	0.391453	0.036117
Fe2	0.013473	0.012585	0.713848	0.023517
Fe3	0.017723	0.038280	1.184962	0.017939
Fe4	0.010846	0.038120	0.641021	0.019412
Fe5	0.020821	0.045142	2.434991	0.022887
Temperature	0.001618	0.001587	0.171350	0.004955

Table 6: Summary table of forecast accuracy metrics for the trained model.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents an innovative monitoring approach based on a Geo-mechanical Digital Twin, which includes real-time inverse analysis and deep-learning techniques to continuously assess slope stability and perform predictive analysis. The method involves automatic updating of a nonlinear finite element model, minimizing the discrepancy with measurement data by establishing a continuous exchange of information between the physical domain of the structure and the virtual domain of the engineering simulation model, thus giving concrete implementation to the digital twin paradigm.

The application of this method represents a significant step forward in the field of geotechnical engineering and risk management. The approach allows the full exploitation of typically available data and techniques, such as numerical terrain models, structural assessments and rock mechanical characterizations through an evolutionary and self-learning digital technology.

The application to stability monitoring of the Mount Geier rock wall near Salorno (Bolzano, Italy) was described in detail. The results showed the method’s ability to provide meaningful information about the slope stability, allowing detailed analysis of its physical behavior and accurate predictions.

Although the proposed approach brings valuable innovations and advantages, it is reasonable to address specific uncertainties that may arise. Estimating the properties of geological materials from limited data can introduce reliability problems due to factors such as incomplete coverage and potential measurement errors. To mitigate these challenges, it is essential that surveys and geotechnical characterizations are carried out by experts, employing robust methodologies and advanced technologies, while leveraging sensitivity analyses and continuously refining models through data-driven feedback loops.

Through interdisciplinary collaborations and the adoption of standardized protocols, this method has the potential to revolutionize the field, making it a scalable and essential resource for addressing the geotechnical challenges of the present and future.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

FE	Finite Element
XFEM	Extended Finite Element Method
UCS	Uniaxial Compressive Strength
GSI	Geological Strength Index
SSR	Shear Strength Reduction
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modeling

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